

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: IBBO DADDY****FIRST NAME: ABDOU****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The Author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 Pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is the purpose of an abstract in an academic paper?
 - To provide a summary of the paper's key points.¹**
 - To introduce the topic of the paper.
 - To present the author's opinions.
 - To showcase the paper's methodology.
2. What is the purpose of a literature review in academic writing?
 - To present original research findings.

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 715.

- To summarize and evaluate existing research on a specific topic.**²
- To provide an overview of the author's personal experiences.
- To speculate about the future of a particular field.
3. Which research method is more concerned with understanding social phenomena in their natural settings?
- Qualitative research.**³
- Quantitative research.
- Mixed-method research.
- Action research.
4. What is the purpose of a doctoral dissertation?
- To demonstrate expertise in a specific area of study.**⁴
- To showcase writing skills.
- To fulfill a graduation requirement.
- To present an opinion.
5. In Turabian style, what is the preferred way to indicate a block quotation in the text?

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, , 352-355.

³ Ibid., 144-145.

⁴ Ibid., 341.

Indenting the entire quotation and omitting quotation marks.⁵

Placing the quotation in italics.

Enclosing the quotation in double quotation marks.

Underlining quotation as a whole.

6. How should a book be cited in the bibliography in Turabian style?

Author's last name, first name. Title of book. Place of publication: Publisher, Year of publication.⁶

Title of book. Author's last name, first name. Publisher, Year of publication.

Author's last name and first name. Title of book. Publisher, Place of publication, Year of publication.

Title of book. Place of publication: Publisher, Year of publication. Author's last name, first name.

7. What type of citation is commonly used in the Turabian style?

Footnotes and endnotes.⁷

In-text citations.

Parenthetical citations.

Bibliographic citations.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: Chicago University Press, 2018), 372-372.

⁶ Ibid., 149.

⁷ Ibid., 147-148.

8. What is the purpose of a research methodology in academic research?

- To outline the theoretical framework of the study.
- To provide a detailed description of the research process.⁸**
- To present the conclusions of the study.
- To speculate on potential future research.

9. What is the role of peer review in academic research?

- To determine the popularity of the research.
- To evaluate the quality and validity of the research.⁹**
- To market the research to a broader audience.
- To provide financial support for the research.

10. What is the purpose of a semicolon in a sentence?

- To separate items in a list.
- To indicate a pause or a break in a sentence.
- To join two independent clauses.¹⁰**
- To indicate possession.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 208.

⁹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 42.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Book: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. (2016) 8-9; Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 320-321.

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